

Appendix S1: Analysis and Model Results

This document lays out R code for all analyses and figures for “Species diversity and dispersal traits alter the potential to increase biodiversity in reconstructed grasslands through spillover,” by: Sperry, Hilfer, Lane, Peterson, Dixon, and Sullivan (revision submitted 2019 to Journal of Ecology). Code was created by Dr. Lauren Sullivan and Dr. Phil Dixon, please contact sullivanll@missouri.edu with questions.

```
#rm(list=ls())
#setwd("")

library(ggplot2)
library(plyr)
library(lme4)
library(lmerTest)
library(lsmeans)
library(emmeans)
library(rmarkdown)
library(MuMIn)

#site-level seeded diversity data
site <- read.csv("./site_info.csv")

#field data and species lists
spp <- read.csv("./field_data_final.csv")
spp$transect <- as.factor(as.character(spp$transect))

#movement trait data
traits <- read.csv("./species_traits_cleaned.csv")
```

First, create the list of desirable species (in traits, `strict_target == "yes"`).

```
#make a vector that is the length of the number of sites
sites <- as.vector(unique(site$site))

#make empty matrices for new data
non_seeded <- matrix(nrow=0, ncol=9)
seeded <- matrix(nrow=0, ncol=9)

# for loop to cycle through all sites and do the same thing at each one
for(s in 1:length(sites)){

  #subset out one site at a time based on the vector "sites"
  temp_site <- subset(spp, site==sites[s])

  #from the single site, subset data by what's been seeded
  temp_site_seeded <- subset(temp_site, type=="seeded")

  #from the single site, subset data by what's in the restored prairies.
  temp_site_restored <- subset(temp_site, type=="restored")
```

```

#scan each row in the restored data to see if their spp is in the seeded mix.
for(i in 1:nrow(temp_site_restored)){

  #store established species if they are not seeded into the vector "non_seeded"
  if(is.element(as.factor(as.character(temp_site_restored[i,6])),
                as.factor(as.character(temp_site_seeded[,6]))=="FALSE"){

    non_seeded <- rbind(non_seeded, temp_site_restored[i,])
  }

  #store established species if they are seeded into the vector "seeded"
  if(is.element(as.factor(as.character(temp_site_restored[i,6])),
                as.factor(as.character(temp_site_seeded[,6]))=="TRUE"){

    seeded <- rbind(seeded, temp_site_restored[i,])
  }
}

#check to make sure the new matrices are populated
#head(seeded)
#head(non_seeded)

```

Analysis 1

Use a linear mixed effect model with a linear effect of distance and a different mean intercept and mean slope for each combination of reconstruction diversity and source type to determine how the slope of desirable species richness with respect to distance from the source boundary changes with different source population type (ag vs remnant), and reconstruction seeded diversity (high vs low).

```

##First pull out the desirable species

#merge non-seeded species with species trait data and site data
spp_traits <- merge(non_seeded, traits, by="species")
spp_traits <- merge(spp_traits, site, by=c("site", "diversity_trt"))

#get an average of the spp number per site per dist for only the target species
spp_traits_strict <- ddply(subset(spp_traits, strict_target=="yes"),
                          .(site, dist, source, seeded_sppno, diversity_trt, transect), summarise,
                          spillover_sppno=length(unique(species)))

#average within distances across transects
spp_traits_strict_avg <- ddply(spp_traits_strict, .(site, dist, source), summarize,
                              avg_spill = mean(spillover_sppno))

spillover_dat <- merge(spp_traits_strict_avg, site, by=c("site"))

spillover_dat$distf <- as.factor(spillover_dat$dist)

# Then run the test: linear distance effect up to 50m
test_lmer <- lmer(avg_spill ~

```

```

source * diversity_trt * dist
+ (dist|site),
subset=(dist < 50),
data=spillover_dat)
anova(test_lmer, type=3)

```

```

## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##
##          Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## source          8.5985   8.5985     1 10.995   9.1789 0.01146 *
## diversity_trt    1.9687   1.9687     1 10.995   2.1016 0.17507
## dist             0.1785   0.1785     1 11.099   0.1906 0.67081
## source:diversity_trt  7.2917   7.2917     1 10.995   7.7838 0.01760 *
## source:dist        2.6844   2.6844     1 11.099   2.8656 0.11834
## diversity_trt:dist  2.6844   2.6844     1 11.099   2.8656 0.11834
## source:diversity_trt:dist 5.2722   5.2722     1 11.099   5.6280 0.03681 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```

r.squaredGLMM(test_lmer)

```

```

##          R2m          R2c
## 0.2663684 0.8396087

```

```

# distance slopes for each group
slope_lmer <- lmer(avg_spill ~ -1+
  source:diversity_trt +source:diversity_trt:dist
  + (dist|site),
  subset=(dist < 50),
  data=spillover_dat)
summary(slope_lmer)

```

```

## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula:
## avg_spill ~ -1 + source:diversity_trt + source:diversity_trt:dist +
##   (dist | site)
## Data: spillover_dat
## Subset: (dist < 50)
##
## REML criterion at convergence: 260.9
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.5499 -0.5090 -0.1576  0.4815  2.2063
##
## Random effects:
##   Groups   Name              Variance Std.Dev. Corr
##   site     (Intercept)  2.536537  1.59265
##           dist          0.001428  0.03779  -0.11
## Residual                    0.936772  0.96787
## Number of obs: 72, groups: site, 15
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error      df
## sourceAg:diversity_trthigh  2.347420   0.920568 11.384400

```

```

## sourceRemnant:diversity_trthigh      2.575000   0.909584 10.878508
## sourceAg:diversity_trtlow            1.075000   1.050297 10.878508
## sourceRemnant:diversity_trtlow      6.600000   0.909584 10.878508
## sourceAg:diversity_trthigh:dist     0.007448   0.026422 12.343218
## sourceRemnant:diversity_trthigh:dist 0.025000   0.024313 10.699177
## sourceAg:diversity_trtlow:dist      0.025000   0.028075 10.699177
## sourceRemnant:diversity_trtlow:dist -0.080000   0.024313 10.699177
##                                     t value Pr(>|t|)
## sourceAg:diversity_trthigh          2.550 0.02637 *
## sourceRemnant:diversity_trthigh     2.831 0.01651 *
## sourceAg:diversity_trtlow           1.024 0.32828
## sourceRemnant:diversity_trtlow      7.256 1.73e-05 ***
## sourceAg:diversity_trthigh:dist     0.282 0.78270
## sourceRemnant:diversity_trthigh:dist 1.028 0.32652
## sourceAg:diversity_trtlow:dist      0.890 0.39279
## sourceRemnant:diversity_trtlow:dist -3.290 0.00746 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##                srcAg:dvrsty_trth  srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trth
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trth      0.000
## srcAg:dvrsty_trtl         0.000          0.000
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trtl      0.000          0.000
## srcAg:dvrsty_trth:       -0.366          0.000
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trth:    0.000         -0.343
## srcAg:dvrsty_trtl:       0.000          0.000
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trtl:    0.000          0.000
##                srcAg:dvrsty_trtl  srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trtl
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trth
## srcAg:dvrsty_trtl
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trtl      0.000
## srcAg:dvrsty_trth:       0.000          0.000
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trth:    0.000          0.000
## srcAg:dvrsty_trtl:      -0.343          0.000
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trtl:    0.000         -0.343
##                srcAg:dvrsty_trth:  srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trth:
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trth
## srcAg:dvrsty_trtl
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trtl
## srcAg:dvrsty_trth:
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trth:    0.000
## srcAg:dvrsty_trtl:      0.000          0.000
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trtl:    0.000          0.000
##                srcAg:dvrsty_trtl:
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trth
## srcAg:dvrsty_trtl
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trtl
## srcAg:dvrsty_trth:
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trth:
## srcAg:dvrsty_trtl:
## srcRmnnt:dvrsty_trtl:    0.000

```

```
# Remnant/low is the only estimated slope that is negative;
# and only one significantly diff from 0
```

```
# means for each group at a range of distances
test_emm <- emmeans(test_lmer,
  c('source','diversity_trt','dist'),
  at=list(dist=c(0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50))
)
test_emm
```

##	source	diversity_trt	dist	emmean	SE	df	lower.CL	upper.CL
##	Ag	high	0	2.35	0.921	11.4	0.3296	4.37
##	Remnant	high	0	2.58	0.910	10.9	0.5703	4.58
##	Ag	low	0	1.07	1.050	10.9	-1.2398	3.39
##	Remnant	low	0	6.60	0.910	10.9	4.5953	8.60
##	Ag	high	5	2.38	0.881	11.2	0.4503	4.32
##	Remnant	high	5	2.70	0.875	10.9	0.7718	4.63
##	Ag	low	5	1.20	1.011	10.9	-1.0264	3.43
##	Remnant	low	5	6.20	0.875	10.9	4.2718	8.13
##	Ag	high	10	2.42	0.860	11.1	0.5318	4.31
##	Remnant	high	10	2.83	0.857	11.0	0.9376	4.71
##	Ag	low	10	1.32	0.990	11.0	-0.8544	3.50
##	Remnant	low	10	5.80	0.857	11.0	3.9126	7.69
##	Ag	high	15	2.46	0.859	11.1	0.5714	4.35
##	Remnant	high	15	2.95	0.856	11.0	1.0650	4.84
##	Ag	low	15	1.45	0.989	11.0	-0.7266	3.63
##	Remnant	low	15	5.40	0.856	11.0	3.5150	7.29
##	Ag	high	20	2.50	0.878	11.2	0.5691	4.42
##	Remnant	high	20	3.08	0.872	10.9	1.1539	5.00
##	Ag	low	20	1.57	1.007	10.9	-0.6433	3.79
##	Remnant	low	20	5.00	0.872	10.9	3.0789	6.92
##	Ag	high	25	2.53	0.915	11.4	0.5268	4.54
##	Remnant	high	25	3.20	0.904	10.9	1.2064	5.19
##	Ag	low	25	1.70	1.044	10.9	-0.6020	4.00
##	Remnant	low	25	4.60	0.904	10.9	2.6064	6.59
##	Ag	high	30	2.57	0.970	11.6	0.4488	4.69
##	Remnant	high	30	3.33	0.951	10.8	1.2265	5.42
##	Ag	low	30	1.82	1.098	10.8	-0.5981	4.25
##	Remnant	low	30	4.20	0.951	10.8	2.1015	6.30
##	Ag	high	35	2.61	1.039	11.8	0.3400	4.88
##	Remnant	high	35	3.45	1.010	10.7	1.2189	5.68
##	Ag	low	35	1.95	1.167	10.7	-0.6262	4.53
##	Remnant	low	35	3.80	1.010	10.7	1.5689	6.03
##	Ag	high	40	2.65	1.119	11.9	0.2059	5.08
##	Remnant	high	40	3.58	1.080	10.7	1.1883	5.96
##	Ag	low	40	2.08	1.247	10.7	-0.6809	4.83
##	Remnant	low	40	3.40	1.080	10.7	1.0133	5.79
##	Ag	high	45	2.68	1.208	12.0	0.0514	5.31
##	Remnant	high	45	3.70	1.159	10.6	1.1391	6.26
##	Ag	low	45	2.20	1.338	10.6	-0.7571	5.16
##	Remnant	low	45	3.00	1.159	10.6	0.4391	5.56
##	Ag	high	50	2.72	1.304	12.1	-0.1195	5.56
##	Remnant	high	50	3.83	1.244	10.6	1.0746	6.58

```
## Ag      low          50  2.33 1.436 10.6 -0.8509    5.50
## Remnant low        50  2.60 1.244 10.6 -0.1504    5.35
##
```

```
## Degrees-of-freedom method: satterthwaite
## Confidence level used: 0.95
```

```
# tests of source, diversity and their interaction
# at each individual distance
# note: these make sense even for distances w/o data
# because the emmeans are based on the slopes.
joint_tests(test_emm, by='dist')
```

```
## dist = 0:
## model term          df1   df2 F.ratio p.value
## source              1 10.99   9.179 0.0115
## diversity_trt       1 10.99   2.102 0.1751
## source:diversity_trt 1 10.99   7.784 0.0176
##
## dist = 5:
## model term          df1   df2 F.ratio p.value
## source              1 11.00   8.484 0.0141
## diversity_trt       1 11.00   1.610 0.2307
## source:diversity_trt 1 11.00   6.590 0.0262
##
## dist = 10:
## model term          df1   df2 F.ratio p.value
## source              1 11.00   7.463 0.0195
## diversity_trt       1 11.00   1.106 0.3155
## source:diversity_trt 1 11.00   5.200 0.0435
##
## dist = 15:
## model term          df1   df2 F.ratio p.value
## source              1 11.00   6.201 0.0300
## diversity_trt       1 11.00   0.653 0.4363
## source:diversity_trt 1 11.00   3.762 0.0785
##
## dist = 20:
## model term          df1   df2 F.ratio p.value
## source              1 10.99   4.849 0.0499
## diversity_trt       1 10.99   0.305 0.5920
## source:diversity_trt 1 10.99   2.451 0.1458
##
## dist = 25:
## model term          df1   df2 F.ratio p.value
## source              1 10.98   3.568 0.0856
## diversity_trt       1 10.98   0.090 0.7698
## source:diversity_trt 1 10.98   1.400 0.2618
##
## dist = 30:
## model term          df1   df2 F.ratio p.value
## source              1 10.97   2.475 0.1441
## diversity_trt       1 10.97   0.004 0.9494
## source:diversity_trt 1 10.97   0.664 0.4325
##
## dist = 35:
```

```

## model term          df1   df2 F.ratio p.value
## source              1 10.96   1.617 0.2299
## diversity_trt       1 10.96   0.021 0.8869
## source:diversity_trt 1 10.96   0.227 0.6433
##
## dist = 40:
## model term          df1   df2 F.ratio p.value
## source              1 10.96   0.989 0.3415
## diversity_trt       1 10.96   0.108 0.7486
## source:diversity_trt 1 10.96   0.030 0.8648
##
## dist = 45:
## model term          df1   df2 F.ratio p.value
## source              1 10.95   0.557 0.4713
## diversity_trt       1 10.95   0.236 0.6369
## source:diversity_trt 1 10.95   0.008 0.9305
##
## dist = 50:
## model term          df1   df2 F.ratio p.value
## source              1 10.96   0.278 0.6087
## diversity_trt       1 10.96   0.383 0.5489
## source:diversity_trt 1 10.96   0.100 0.7572

```

#Figure 2

```

##average across all sites by source
Fig2_stats <- ddply(spillover_dat, .(dist, source, diversity_trt), summarise,
  meanspp = mean(avg_spill),
  sespp = sd(avg_spill)/sqrt(length((avg_spill))))

Fig2_stats$trt_group<-paste(Fig2_stats$source, Fig2_stats$diversity_trt)
Fig2_stats$trt_group<-factor(Fig2_stats$trt_group)

#to allow for plotting on a continuous scale.
Fig2_stats$dist <- as.numeric(as.character(Fig2_stats$dist))

ggplot(Fig2_stats)+
  geom_pointrange(aes(x=dist, y=meanspp, ymin=meanspp-sespp, ymax=meanspp+sespp,
    colour=trt_group,shape=trt_group), alpha = .7,
    size=1.5,position=position_dodge(width=4))+
  theme_bw()+
  theme(aspect.ratio=1)+
  scale_linetype_manual(values=c(1,2,1,2),name="Reconstruction Type")+
  scale_shape_manual(name="Reconstruction Type",values=c(17,19,17,19))+
  geom_line(aes(x=dist, y=meanspp, colour=trt_group, linetype=trt_group), alpha=.5,
    size=1.25,position=position_dodge(width=4))+
  labs(x="Distance from Source (m)",y="Spillover Species Richness +/-SE")+
  scale_color_manual(values=c("goldenrod1", "goldenrod1","deepskyblue3",
    "deepskyblue3"),name = "Reconstruction Type")+
  theme(axis.text=element_text(size=14))+
  theme(axis.title=element_text(size=16, face="bold"))+
  theme(legend.title=element_text(size=16))+
  theme(legend.text=element_text(size=14))+
  ylim(0,8)

```


Analysis 2

Next, examine how the dispersal traits - specifically a species's dispersal mode, alters a species' spillover occurrence in plots (or the number of plots desirable species occurred up in summed across all transects at low diversity sites adjacent to remnants). Then create Figure 3

```
#spillover species are in low diversity sites with remnant sources across both transects
spp_all <- merge(spp, traits, by="species")
spill_strict <- subset(spp_all, strict_target == "yes" & source == "Remnant" &
  diversity_trt == "low" & transect != "NA")

spill_strict <- spill_strict[,c(1:3, 5:6)]

#remove PANVIR because it was seeded at the low diversity sites it occurs.
#This was removed in the previous step for Analysis 1 so not necessary there.
spill_all <- subset(spill_strict, species != "PANVIR")

spill_all$dist <- as.factor(as.character(spill_all$dist))

#calculate spillover occurrence (total number of plots a spillover species occurs in)
spill_all_occ <- dplyr::ddply(spill_all, .(species), summarise,
  occurrence = length(transect))

spill_all_occ_traits <- merge(spill_all_occ, traits, by="species", all.x=TRUE)

spill_all_occ_traits <- subset(spill_all_occ_traits, species != "CARTET")#remove CARTET
spill_all_occ_traits$species <- as.factor(as.character(spill_all_occ_traits$species))
```

```

#run test
test2 <- aov(log(occurrence) ~ seed_dispersal, data=spill_all_occ_traits)
summary(test2)

##              Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
## seed_dispersal  2  7.383   3.692   4.719 0.0155 *
## Residuals      34 26.600   0.782
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

TukeyHSD(test2, "seed_dispersal", ordered = TRUE)

## Tukey multiple comparisons of means
## 95% family-wise confidence level
## factor levels have been ordered
##
## Fit: aov(formula = log(occurrence) ~ seed_dispersal, data = spill_all_occ_traits)
##
## $seed_dispersal
##              diff            lwr            upr            p adj
## wind-unassisted  0.87074685  0.08851094  1.652983  0.0264099
## animal-unassisted 0.95070842 -0.07851393  1.979931  0.0749605
## animal-wind      0.07996158 -0.97763669  1.137560  0.9812654

#qqnorm(spill_all_occ_traits$occurrence) #visual of normality.
#confirm heteroscedasticity isn't a problem.
bartlett.test(log(occurrence) ~ seed_dispersal, data=spill_all_occ_traits)

##
## Bartlett test of homogeneity of variances
##
## data: log(occurrence) by seed_dispersal
## Bartlett's K-squared = 0.41985, df = 2, p-value = 0.8106

Fig3_stats <- ddply(spill_all_occ_traits, .(seed_dispersal), summarise,
  mean_occ = mean(occurrence, na.rm=TRUE),
  se_occ = sd(occurrence, na.rm=TRUE)/sqrt(length(occurrence)))

Fig3_stats$seed_dispersal <- factor(Fig3_stats$seed_dispersal,
  levels = c("unassisted", "wind", "animal"))

#Figure 3
ggplot(subset(Fig3_stats, seed_dispersal != "NA" ))+
  geom_pointrange(aes(x=seed_dispersal, y=mean_occ, ymin=mean_occ-se_occ,
    ymax=mean_occ+se_occ),size=1.5, alpha = 1)+
  theme_bw()+
  theme(aspect.ratio=1)+
  theme(axis.text=element_text(size=14))+
  theme(axis.title=element_text(size=16, face="bold"))+
  xlab("Seed Dispersal Mode")+
  ylab("Spillover Occurrence +/-SE")

```


#no significant results for the other dispersal modes

```
test3 <- aov(log(occurrence) ~ pollen_dispersal, data=spill_all_occ_traits)
summary(test3)
```

```
##                Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
## pollen_dispersal  1  0.00  0.000      0  0.996
## Residuals        35 33.98  0.971
```

```
test4 <- aov(log(occurrence) ~ vegetative_dispersal, data=spill_all_occ_traits)
summary(test4)
```

```
##                Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
## vegetative_dispersal  3  1.12  0.3722  0.374  0.772
## Residuals           33 32.87  0.9960
```